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Abstract

The acquisition of a foreign language is a lengthy process. Learned foreign words go into memory, but later the learners may forget them or, after repetition for varying lengths of time, they can memorize them. Forgetting foreign words has two degrees: forgetting the foreign words and their meaning in the native language or forgetting only the meaning of the foreign words in the native language. Learners must learn the forgotten foreign words again, like unknown words. Foreign language learners use only part of the learned words actively through speaking or writing, but there are words that learners can only understand when they listen or read. This division is the basis of the division of memory into active and passive. This publication examines the dynamics of the process of foreign language learning.

Keywords: process of foreign language learning; passive and active vocabulary; human reason and memory; memorizing of foreign language words; second-language attrition; language retention; model of how foreign languages work in the human mind

*Research in Support of Modern Foreign Language Learning***1. Introduction**

Mastering foreign languages has always been an intriguing issue. This issue is covered in a lot of linguistics articles. Although numerous methodologies for learning foreign languages have been developed, there is still more to discover. The two key issues that philologists are continuously concerned with are the effective learning of foreign languages and overcoming the negative effects of losing language knowledge.

Learning a foreign language is a challenging and creative process. The need to master various skills necessary for language proficiency causes the challenge. Children learn to read and write as they begin school, but they begin to understand and speak their native language at a very young age. On the contrary, when humans learn a second language, these activities can go on at the same time.

Finding the ideal balance between the development of fundamental language skills—listening and reading with comprehension, as well as speaking and writing in a foreign language—is necessary for success in language acquisition.

It is debatable whether simultaneous development of all skills and which teaching techniques are the most practical ways to learn a foreign language. Responses to these questions include how we can develop all skills and which teaching techniques are the most practical ways to learn a foreign language. Before addressing this issue, it is better to first consider the factors that influence foreign language acquisition.

There are numerous factors that influence language acquisition, and they can be divided into two categories: those that are helpful and those that are harmful.

The most effective method for learning a foreign language is the one that requires the least amount of effort. You can achieve the best outcomes by finding the right ratio of time spent speaking, listening, reading,

and writing in a foreign language. This should also include a pleasant learning environment, which includes the use of audio-visual aids, educational materials, and a student's alert and unhurried frame of mind. Special consideration should be given to the circumstances that have a detrimental impact on learning, such as anything that makes learning too difficult or when learning advances at an inappropriate rate.

The two key issues with learning foreign languages are the inability to keep in memory the words learned and the challenge of communicating in a foreign language. Even when the student understands the other person very well, it may be difficult to respond in a foreign language. Also, there is a decline in language skills, even among people who have previously achieved language ability but do not continue to practice a foreign language.

2. Human mind components

Scientists are interested in the role of human minds since people have a constant desire to improve their intellectual skills. The ability of the human intellect is extensive. The ability for thought and analysis belongs to the human mind. There are some theories that explain how the mind works. Some psychologists believe that the mind's essential components are only the "highest" intellectual processes, like reason and memory.

Memory and reasoning serve complementary functions. Memory serves to maintain access to previously acquired information (including information recently generated in the course of a task) while reasoning seeks to derive new information from the old. [1]

3. Passive and Active vocabulary

There are two types of vocabulary: active and passive. Humans' active vocabulary is the one that is used in both their private and public lives on a regular basis. The higher the vocabulary, the more advanced the speaker's linguistic culture. Words that a person knows

and can understand to varied degrees but does not actively use when speaking are included in their passive vocabulary. The native language's vocabulary is always larger than that of other languages. The vocabulary of the foreign language may theoretically grow to be larger than that of the native language, but this shows that the foreign language has already supplanted the native language. This is possible for people who reside in a foreign nation and only speak the local language. [2]

Receptive and productive vocabulary are other names for passive and active words. Grammar and vocabulary are the fundamental building blocks of language. The time and effort needed to master these two fundamental concepts in a foreign language are the greatest. It is common knowledge that reading and listening comprehension in a foreign language are always simpler than speaking and writing. In addition, the words we use are far less typical than the ones we understand. Each of these things has an explanation, and it's crucial to recognize and comprehend this while developing strategies for learning other languages. [3]

Because of language learning and the natural deterioration of language if it is not consistently used, human active and passive vocabulary knowledge is continuously changing. People employ their regular vocabulary, pick up unfamiliar words and lose old ones, experiment with some updated terms, and learn about other people's vocabularies. Humans' active and passive vocabularies may easily switch words back and forth over time, but their passive vocabularies will always be much larger.

4. Prevention of attrition and promotion of retention

The loss of second-language ability, also referred to as "second-language attrition", happens whenever a learner uses the second language insufficiently. When learners reach fluency or competence, their language abilities typically begin to deteriorate because of a decrease in interaction with the second language, whether from a loss of communication with others or other factors. Foreign language attrition is the gradual decline in language ability, usually because of a decrease in language input and use.

Language retention, which should be defined as the deliberate participation in actions that will slow or impede attrition, is the reverse of language attrition.

There are at least two components to retention: preserving or generating possibilities for both language input information and production. The latter refers to the anticipation of output that results from genuine interaction with others, not just the expression of utterances for practice. [4]

5. Author's thesis for Dynamic model of foreign language learning

The human mind has two basic faculties: reason and memory. Reason and memory have their own specific functions that complement each other. Physiologically healthy people have equally well-developed reason and memory. Greater deviations in either direction are more likely to represent some sort of disease state. Foreign language learning takes time and effort. There are various steps involved in understanding, learning, and using unfamiliar words. The repetition of previously forgotten words is a necessary part of learning a foreign language because of the human inclination to forget. Reason and memory are the two basic cognitive processes involved in learning a foreign language. These two mental functions of the human mind interact and support one another. Both skills are interdependent, meaning they complement each other. Reason takes the lead while learning foreign language grammar, and memory takes the lead when learning new vocabulary. Everyone has a vocabulary that is both passive and active, according to theory. This is governed by the memory's ability for storing passive and active language information, or, more specifically, by the distinction between the memory's ability for passively storing lexical objects and that for actively processing them.

My understanding is that the model of how foreign languages function in the human mind has four sectors that make interconnections.

The dynamic model of foreign language learning has the following interconnected sectors (fig. 1):

1. Senses: hearing and sight
2. Language skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing
3. Reason
4. Memory

Each of the functional sectors has sub-sectors with specific duties. All functional sectors and subsectors interact.

DYNAMIC MODEL OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING				
skills	by listening	by reading	by speaking	by writing
reason	comprehension	comprehension	thinking	thinking
decode	translation	translation	translation	translation
time	for reception	for reception	for production	for production
memory	UPPER LAYER			
result	Active vocabulary	Foreign words that are well understood and actively used by the language learner		
	BASIC LAYER			
	Passive vocabulary	Foreign words that the language learner comprehends but cannot actively use		
	LOWER LAYER			
	Words for review	Foreign words that the learner studies but forgets the meanings in their native tongue		
	DEEP LAYER			
	Forgotten words	Foreign words that were learned but fully forgotten and need to be relearned		
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Fig. 1

5.1. Reception of unfamiliar foreign words by listening and reading

Obtaining information in a foreign language, also called "input information", is done through the sensory skills of hearing and vision. My understanding is that the first memorization of vocabulary depends primarily on attention and the duration of contact with the new and unfamiliar foreign words. Effective acquisition of new vocabulary requires that, when learning texts, they must be heard repeatedly with quality speech reproduced. After listening to the text twice, it is good to listen to it again, but at the same time, the students should visually follow the written text. It is recommended that texts that are studied within one lesson is good to have 3–4 unfamiliar foreign words that are repeated several times in the text. It is also recommended that learners go through the text at least three times without translating the unfamiliar words. The goal is first to memorize only the foreign word without its translation into the learner's native language. During this stage, the learner is expected to understand the meaning of the unfamiliar words from the context, i.e., reason is involved. After translating the word with a dictionary, the text must be read and translated again. It is recommended that after the translation of the text, the unfamiliar words be included in the grammar exercises for learners to hear other meanings of the words and to reinforce their memorization. It is advisable to give more time and attention to unfamiliar words in a foreign language when learning them for the first time. Attention and timing for the first acquisition of new vocabulary are crucial for the length of time foreign words remain in the learner's memory.

5.2. Memory and stages of foreign language memorization

According to the model, the memory is divided into four layers. The uppermost layer, the closest to the

layer of the mind, is used for the active foreign language vocabulary. The active vocabulary is that which is used in speaking and writing. The active vocabulary reflects the level of proficiency in the language. The level of a foreign language's active vocabulary depends on the effort that is put into learning the language, but it also depends on the level of vocabulary mastered in the native language. The foreign language vocabulary cannot be richer than the native language vocabulary.

The passive foreign language vocabulary is in the second memory layer. This is the vocabulary of words that the foreign language learner understands when listening or reading but is unable to reproduce when speaking or writing. This layer of memory is the most dynamic because, in learning a foreign language, a part of the words in passive vocabulary go to the active vocabulary but could also go to the lower third layer of memory if they are not used.

The third layer of memory is the vocabulary of foreign words whose meaning in the native language is unknown. In this layer of memory are the words that are in the process of being assimilated and transferred to some of the upper layers of memory.

The fourth layer of memory is the "forgotten" foreign words, which have not completely disappeared from the deep memory. In fact, these are the words that are forgotten because they are not used. The recovery of "forgotten" foreign words is significantly easier than learning new unfamiliar foreign words.

5.3. Dynamics of the process of foreign language word memorization, attrition, and promotion of retention

The human mind has three properties that influence the rate of foreign language acquisition, retention, and loss. The capacity of memory, attrition, and retention of the learned vocabulary and grammar of the foreign language are what determine the dynamics of

learning a foreign language. After a foreign word is encountered and learned, it remains in active memory for a short time. Usually, the words pass to some of the lower layers of the foreign language's memory. Knowledge of a foreign language is both passive and active. The passive level is the lower one, and the vocabulary in it is the basic vocabulary. Passive vocabulary is upgraded during the time when the foreign language is learned. After frequent listening and reading of the words from the passive vocabulary, some of them pass into active memory. The words in active memory can go to passive memory when they are not frequently used.

Methods: Practical experience in learning foreign languages, theoretical knowledge, and descriptive method is applied by the author of the article.

Conclusion: The article pays special attention to the efficient acquisition and memory retention of the vocabulary of foreign languages, which are the main problems in their study. The author of the article believes that since nature has universally applicable laws and that man is a product of those laws, it is best to learn a foreign language in a natural way through listening comprehension. Practical results prove that the acquisition of a foreign language is easier with listening comprehension and constant review that is learned and kept permanently in the memory. The author's maxim is that foreign language learning should keep the foreign language alive through listening comprehension, reading comprehension, and communicating in person with native speakers.

Proposal for techniques and strategies for foreign language learning:

The strategies are based on following principals:

1. Vocabulary – to be used the word list of Oxford Learner's Dictionaries base on first list of 3000 words by CERF level and second list of 5000 words by CERF level which includes the first list words. [5]

2. The words of both lists are divided in 6 levels: A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2.

3. All lessons must be strictly based on currently studied list of words beginning with list of 3000 words, and later with list 5000 words and the proper level (A1 or A2 or B1 or B2 or C1 or C2). The words from previous levels must be also included to the texts.

4. It is recommended that the studied material be easy to understand. The new words should be in accordance with the word sheet, as per point 3. The new words from the text should also be used in the exercises. Every 3–5 lessons have a summary lesson, including all new words and grammar from the previous lessons. It is recommended to repeatedly listen to the lessons and to practice listening to the text and reading at the same time.

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